

CONCEPT TEACHING STRATEGIES

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Annotation: this article discusses about concepts types and concept teaching strategies. Besides, using concepts in teaching there are some benefits that can be helpful to develop students' critical thinking and analyzing their own thinking processes.

Key words: concept, sensory concept, basic concept, abstract concept.

Teaching concepts is a process that involves teacher's attitude towards the concepts and students' deep and wide understanding about concepts and requires enough knowledge and experience. Concepts are powerful, broad and abstract organizing ideas that may be transdisciplinary or subject-based. They can help to build understanding across, between and beyond subjects. Concepts in teaching are knowledge tools that can identify, define, explain, analyze and demonstrate real-life elements and events. These are broad ideas that are in many instances, true across geographical and cultural boundaries. H. Lynn Erickson (2008) states that a concept is a "a big idea"- a principle or notion that is enduring and is not constrained by a particular origin, subject matter or place in time. Concepts represent ideas that are broad, abstract, timeless and universal. It should be known that there are two main kinds of concepts: sensory concepts and abstract concepts. According to Edward Kame'enui and Simmons (1990) a sensory or basic concept is a concept whose examples have features that can be seen, smelled, touched, tastes, or heard all at once in one place. This type of concept can be taught easily by the help of pictures, songs, videos, real materials and etc. Students do not have any difficulties in using and understanding them. Sensory concepts are usually explained with objects that can be seen, touched, smelled, tasted and heard. For example, *birds, bread, flowers, sounds* and *animals*. The second type of concept is an abstract concept. It is an idea that people can comprehend that does not have any physical form. The ability to identify, understand and communicate abstract concepts is a foundational element of human intelligence. It is a big mistake to think that all abstract concepts are not real as they can be documented with evidence. All languages have words for abstract concepts. For instance, the words *freedom, happiness, death*, etc. They are completely abstract concepts that can not be directly perceived or measured. Teaching and learning new languages allow any individual to acquire new abstract concepts and can result in new thought processes. There are a lot of benefits of teaching concepts. Concepts drive the learning; embed students' ideas, theories, questions and interests; promote collaboration and construction of meaning; promote connections across the curriculum; embed skills and assets as a part of the learning process; promote critical thinking and problem solving; focus on the why and how of learning; unfold in response to students; involve the student as an active participant in their learning and promote curiosity, wonderment and the desire to understand. There are some steps of using concept teaching in the classroom: selecting Big Idea concepts and teachers should determine the best approaches: inductive through direct presentation of the concept first or the next approach is deductive (concept attainment) through examples/nonexamples and guided discovery. The second step is clarifying aims and establishing a "hook" to draw students' attention in; the next step is getting students to demonstrate their understanding

i.e., the process in which teachers have a chance to check students' comprehension about concepts and the last step is to employ higher-level questioning and discussion strategies that help students analyze their own thinking processes.

In conclusion, teaching concepts require deep understanding and experience that both teachers and students should possess. Concept teaching is a continuous process in which students can develop not only their general knowledge but also enlarge their horizons.

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